

SUPPORTING INFORMATION FOR “REMODELING MALE COERCION AND THE EVOLUTION OF SEXUAL
AUTONOMY BY MATE CHOICE”

APPENDICES S1, S2, & S3

S.S. SNOW & R.O. PRUM

APPENDIX S1: DEVELOPMENT OF THE MAIN MODEL RECURSION EQUATIONS

Here we develop the recursion equations of the main model presented in the text. For detailed, reproducible code, including specifications for parameter values and numerical simulations, see the Mathematica notebook in Supporting Information File S1.

Our model includes the influences of five traits: female preference for male display, male display, male propensity/ability to sexually coerce, female remodeling preference, and the male autonomy-enhancing trait. As described in the main text, we assume that both female preference for male display and the male coercion trait are fixed in the population, functionally yielding a three-locus system.

We employ autosomal, haploid genetics with loci having sex-linked expression. The three diallelic loci (T for male display, B for male autonomy-enhancing trait, and R for female remodeling preference; see table 1 for definitions) give eight possible genotypes, $T_1B_1R_1$, $T_2B_1R_1$, $T_1B_2R_1$, $T_2B_2R_1$, $T_1B_1R_2$, $T_2B_1R_2$, $T_1B_2R_2$, and $T_2B_2R_2$, which we will index here as G_1 through G_8 .

Viability selection

In males:

Males carrying the T_2 allele express a costly display trait such that they have a probability of $(1-s_t)$ of surviving until the mating season relative to a T_1 male. Males carrying the B_2 allele similarly pay a viability cost for producing the autonomy-enhancing trait such that they have a $(1-s_b)$ chance of survival relative to a male with the B_1 allele. Accordingly, adapting the notation of Dhole *et al.* (2018), the frequency of a genotype G_i in males after viability selection is given by

$$g'_{im} = \frac{(1 - \theta_i s_t)(1 - \zeta_i s_b) g_{im}}{\sum_i (1 - \theta_i s_t)(1 - \zeta_i s_b) g_{im}}$$

where g_{im} is the frequency of genotype G_i in males before viability selection. If the allele at the T locus for G_i is T_2 (i is even), then $\theta_i = 1$, and $\theta_i = 0$ otherwise. If the allele at the B locus is B_2 ($i \bmod 4$ is 3 or 0), $\zeta_i = 1$, and $\zeta_i = 0$ otherwise. The prime notation is a reminder that the new frequency has been adjusted by viability selection; this will carry through the rest of the section.

In females:

Females carrying the R_2 allele for female remodeling preference pay a small differential viability cost such that R_2 females have a $(1-s_r)$ chance of surviving to mate relative to R_1 females. The frequency of a genotype G_j in females after viability selection is given by

$$g'_{j_f} = \frac{(1 - \psi_j s_r) g_{j_f}}{\sum_j (1 - \psi_j s_r) g_{j_f}}$$

where g_{j_f} is the frequency of genotype G_j in females before viability selection. If the allele at the R locus is R_1 ($j < 5$), $\psi_j = 0$, and $\psi_j = 1$ otherwise.

Sexual selection

After viability selection, mating occurs according to the scheme laid out in figure 1 and in the frequencies summarized in table 2 in the main text. Females with the remodeling preference (the R_2 allele) prefer to visit the territories of males with the autonomy-enhancing trait (the B_2 allele) by a factor of $(1+a_b)$. Once on a territory, the male may coerce them into mating without giving the female the opportunity to evaluate the male's display with a probability c . Without coercion, females prefer to mate with attractive T_2 males by a factor of $(1+a_t)$. (Without coercion, if $a_t=0$, females are equally likely to accept or reject the male, i.e., the probability of accepting the male is $1/2$). The male autonomy-enhancing trait, B_2 , confers protection from coercion given by the parameter γ such that females that visit territories of B_2 males have an adjusted likelihood of coercion $c(1-\gamma)$.

We assume that females continue visiting territories until they ultimately choose a male or are coerced. The ultimate frequency of the various pairings between male and female genotypes can be derived as follows:

If the probabilities that a female with a particular genotype mates with a male of genotype i on her initial visit are given by the vector p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n , let

$$q = 1 - \sum_i^n p_i$$

where q is the probability that a female goes unmated after the first round of visits. The ultimate frequency of a particular pairing P_i after all visits are done will be given by the geometric series

$$P_i = p_i + p_i q + p_i q^2 + \dots$$

which simplifies to

$$P_i = \frac{p_i}{1 - q}$$

Since all P_i are adjusted by the same normalization factor, then we know that the ultimate frequency ratio will be equal to the probability ratio for the 1-visit expressions for any number of visits, with the normalization factor being the sum of the 1-visit probabilities in the case of infinite visits.

Thus, the final frequencies of the genotype pairings will be the initial probabilities that a particular genotype of female mates with each type of male on her first visit, normalized by the sum of the initial probabilities for that female genotype.

Formally, the frequency of matings between male genotype i and female genotype j is given by:

$$M_{ij} = g'_{jf} \frac{g'_{im} \frac{(\sigma_{ij} a_b + 1)}{z_b} \left(\frac{c(1 - \varepsilon_i \gamma) + (1 - c(1 - \varepsilon_i \gamma)) \left(\frac{\omega_i a_t + 1}{a_t + 2} \right)}{z} \right)}{z}$$

where

$$z = \sum_i g'_{im} \frac{(\sigma_{ij} a_b + 1)}{z_b} \left(\frac{c(1 - \varepsilon_i \gamma) + (1 - c(1 - \varepsilon_i \gamma)) \left(\frac{\omega_i a_t + 1}{a_t + 2} \right)}{z} \right)$$

$$z_b = b'_{1m} + (\rho_j a_b + 1) b'_{2m}$$

and where b'_{1m} and b'_{2m} are the frequencies of the two B alleles within males after viability selection, such that $b'_{1m} = g'_{1m} + g'_{2m} + g'_{5m} + g'_{6m}$ and $b'_{2m} = g'_{3m} + g'_{4m} + g'_{7m} + g'_{8m}$.

If the male allele at the B locus for genotype G_i is B_1 ($i=1, 2, 5$ or 6), $\varepsilon_i = 0$. If the male allele at the B locus for G_i is B_2 ($i=3, 4, 7$ or 8), $\varepsilon_i = 1$.

If the male allele at the T locus for G_i is T_2 (i is even), then $\omega_i = 1$, and $\omega_i = 0$ otherwise.

If the female allele at the R locus for G_j is R_2 ($j > 4$), $\rho_j = 1$, and $\rho_j = 0$ otherwise.

Finally, if the male allele at the B locus for G_i is B_2 ($i=3, 4, 7$ or 8) **and** the female allele at the R locus for G_j is R_2 ($j > 4$), then $\sigma_{ij} = 1$, and $\sigma_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.

Note that the z_b terms ultimately cancel out, but we have left them in place here to preserve the interpretation of the numerator of the M_{ij} expression as the probability that a female of genotype G_j mates with a male of genotype G_i on her first territory visit.

For reference, the “x” terms used in the summary mating matrix in table 2 in the main text correspond to the male genotype frequencies after viability selection as follows:

$$x'_{11} = g'_{1m} + g'_{5m}$$

$$x'_{21} = g'_{2_m} + g'_{6_m}$$

$$x'_{12} = g'_{3_m} + g'_{7_m}$$

$$x'_{22} = g'_{4_m} + g'_{8_m}$$

Similarly, the “y” terms representing the frequencies of the two R alleles within females after viability selection used in table 2 correspond to the female genotype frequencies after selection such that:

$$y'_{.1} = g'_{1_f} + g'_{2_f} + g'_{3_f} + g'_{4_f}$$

$$y'_{.2} = g'_{5_f} + g'_{6_f} + g'_{7_f} + g'_{8_f}$$

Recombination and mutation

After viability selection and mating, there is standard free recombination ($r=1/2$), yielding the zygote genotypes. Finally, we use biased mutation in our model as a simple mechanism for the purpose of maintaining diversity at the male display locus, T. Every generation, a portion u of the genotypes having the T_2 allele mutates into the corresponding genotype having the T_1 allele. Again adapting the notation of Dhole *et al.* (2018), the frequency of a genotype after mutation is therefore given by

$$g_{i_u} = g_i + \theta_i g_j u - (1 - \theta_i) g_i u$$

where $\theta_i = 0$ if the allele at the T locus is T_2 (i is even), and $\theta_i = 1$ otherwise, and $j = i + 1$.

With the expressions for genotype frequencies after viability selection, mating, recombination and mutation each generation in hand, we can generate the recursion equations for the genotype frequencies used in our numerical simulations and other analyses (e.g., $\Delta g_i = g_{i_{\tau+1}} - g_{i_{\tau}}$, where $g_{i_{\tau+1}}$ is the frequency of genotype G_i after one round of selection, mating, etc.). For analysis and visualization, we transformed these eight recursion equations into the equivalent but more easily interpretable seven equations for the allele frequencies at the three loci and first- and second-order linkage disequilibria (Bennett 1952).

APPENDIX S2: DERIVATION OF INITIAL FREQUENCY FOR THE T_2 ALLELE FOR SIMULATIONS, AND RELATED PARAMETER CONSTRAINTS

We extended the Kirkpatrick (1982) two-locus sexual selection model to include sexually coercive male behavior (c) and mutation bias at the male display trait locus (T) and mimicking the female visitation scheme we use in the main model. We analytically solve the model for the case where the female preference allele, P_2 , is equal to one. This yields an expression for a stable equilibrium for T_2 between zero and one that represents a balance of female preference, male

display, male coercive behavior, viability selection, and biased mutation. We use this to calculate the starting frequency for T_2 in the full model. The equilibrium expression also dictates the minimum value for the a_i parameter such that these conditions still hold for our simulations. Finally, we can use the equilibrium expression to calculate the initial adjusted realized magnitude of a_i for a given level of coercion.

Reproducible code for this model and analysis can be found in the Mathematica notebook in Supporting Information File S2.

The model includes two diallelic loci (P for female preference, and T for male display trait), yielding four possible genotypes: T_1P_1 , T_1P_2 , T_2P_1 , and T_2P_2 which we will index here as G_1 through G_4 .

Viability Selection

Just as in the main model, males carrying the T_2 allele express a costly display trait that decreases their relative survival to reproduction by a factor of $(1-s_i)$. Thus, the frequency of a genotype G_i in males after viability selection is given by

$$g'_{i_m} = \frac{(1 - \theta_i s_t) g_{i_m}}{\sum_i (1 - \theta_i s_t) g_{i_m}}$$

where g_{i_m} is the frequency of genotype G_i in males before viability selection. If the allele at the T locus for G_i is T_2 ($i > 2$), then $\theta_i = 1$, and $\theta_i = 0$ otherwise.

Sexual Selection

Without coercion, P_1 female mate randomly with respect to the male T allele, and P_2 females prefer to mate with attractive T_2 males by a factor of $(1+a_i)$ (Note that this formulation differs slightly from the preference rule in Kirkpatrick 1982; our parameterization yields random mating at $a_i=0$). Just as in the main model, we add the effect of male coercive behavior such that a male may coerce a female that visits them into mating without giving the female the opportunity to evaluate the male's display with a probability c . The frequency of matings between male genotype i and female genotype j is given by:

$$M_{ij} = g'_{j_f} \frac{g'_{i_m} \left(c + (1 - c) \left(\frac{\omega_{ij} a_t + 1}{\phi_j a_t + 2} \right) \right)}{z}$$

where

$$z = \sum_i g'_{i_m} \left(c + (1 - c) \left(\frac{\omega_{ij} a_t + 1}{\phi_j a_t + 2} \right) \right).$$

If the allele at the female P locus for G_j is P_2 ($j = 2$ or 4), then $\phi_j = 1$, and $\phi_j = 0$ otherwise. If the allele at the male T locus for G_i is T_2 ($i > 2$) **and** the allele at the female P locus for G_j is P_2 ($j = 2$ or 4), then $\omega_{ij} = 1$, and $\omega_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.

Recombination and mutation

After viability selection and assortative mating, free recombination follows zygote formation to yield new genotype frequencies, to which biased mutation is applied in exactly the manner described in section S1.1 for the main model.

Identification and stability of the intermediate equilibrium for the T_2 allele

From our expressions for per-generation change in genotype frequencies, we can generate recursion equations for allele frequencies t_2 and p_2 and for the linkage disequilibrium D_{TP} (see the Mathematica notebook in Supporting Information File S2 for the full recursion equations).

Assuming female preference for display is fixed ($p_2 = 1$ and $D_{TP} = 0$), the recursion equation for the frequency of the T_2 allele becomes

$$\Delta t_2 = \frac{t_2 \left(\begin{array}{c} a_t(-u+1)t_2(c+s_t-1) + cu + c - us_t + u + s_t - 1 \\ -(c+1)(u(s_t t_2 + s_t - 2) + s_t(t_2 - 1)) \end{array} \right)}{2t_2(a_t(c+s_t-1) + cs_t + s_t) - 2(a_t c + c + 1)}.$$

Setting $\Delta t_2 = 0$ and solving yields two equilibrium solutions, one at zero and one non-zero solution. The non-zero equilibrium expression for t_2 (Eq. 1 in the main text) is

$$\hat{t}_2 = \frac{1 - u + \frac{2(1 + c + a_t c)u}{s_t + cs_t + a_t(c + s_t - 1)}}{1 + u}.$$

By differentiating the expression for Δt_2 with respect to t_2 and then setting $t_2 = \hat{t}_2$ and rearranging, it can be shown that the equilibrium with an intermediate frequency at \hat{t}_2 will be stable (the sign of the expression will be negative) given that $0 < s_t < 1$, and $0 < u < 1$, as long as

$$a_t > \frac{1 + u}{(u - 1)(s_t - 1)} - 1$$

and

$$0 < c < \frac{a_t - 2u - a_t u + (1 + a_t)(u - 1)s_t}{a_t + 2u + a_t u + s_t - us_t}$$

Thus, in our numerical simulations (presented in detail in the Mathematica notebook in Supporting Information File S1, and the results of which we report in the main text), we always chose sets of parameters such that the values of a_t and c were consistent with (large enough and small enough, respectively) the stability of $t_2 = \hat{t}_2$ in the absence of remodeling. This ensures a scenario at the beginning of our simulations wherein there is an initial balance between coercion and display (and selection and mutation) with females still realizing their mate preference to some extent despite the effect of coercion.

Initial adjusted realized magnitude of female preference

We can visualize the overall effect of coercion by asking what adjusted value of a_t would produce the equivalent equilibrium value of \hat{t}_2 if coercion were absent.

Evaluating \hat{t}_2 at $c=0$ and $a_t = a_{t\text{adj}}$ yields:

$$\hat{t}_2|_{\{c=0, a_t=a_{t\text{adj}}\}} = \frac{1 - u + \frac{2u}{a_{t\text{adj}}(s_t - 1) + s_t}}{1 + u}$$

We can then solve the equation

$$\hat{t}_2 = \hat{t}_2|_{\{c=0, a_t=a_{t\text{adj}}\}}$$

to get the expression

$$a_{t\text{adj}} = \frac{a_t(1 - c)}{c(a_t + 1) + 1}$$

This is the same as the expression in Eq. 2 in the main text. The expression for $a_{t\text{adj}}$ holds as long as the conditions outlined above for the stable initial non-zero T_2 equilibrium are met. See the Mathematica notebook in Supporting Information File S2 for the full calculations.

APPENDIX S3: SPECIFICATION OF THE MODEL EXAMINING SELECTION FOR MORE PROTECTIVE AUTONOMY-ENHANCING TRAITS

This version of the model, referenced in the subsection “*Selection for more protective autonomy-enhancing traits*” in the main text is nearly identical to the main model presented in the paper and above in Appendix S1 (the schemes and parameterizations for viability selection, recombination, and mutation are the same) but it employs an altered mating matrix. We use this as a complementary approach to parse the effects of “Fisherian” sexual selection and the remodeling process and to explore the force of selection on protective autonomy-enhancing traits as compared to other, less protective, or simply arbitrarily attractive traits for which females have

similarly strong preferences. Therefore, in this case, R₂ females prefer B₂ males by a factor of (1+a_b), but, rather than visit territories randomly, R₁ females have an equally strong preference for (non-protective) B₁ males, such that their territory visits are biased towards B₁ males also by the same factor (1+a_b).

All females still prefer T₂ males by a factor of (1+a_t). Finally, male coercive behavior and protection from coercion work as in the main model, with all males having the ability to coerce (with a likelihood of success *c*) and only B₂ males having the possibility of producing a trait that protects against coercion with an effectiveness γ . Apart from the mating biased toward B₁ males associated with R₁ females, mating takes place by exactly the same process as described above and in Figure 1.

Thus, using the same indices for genotypes in males and females as above, the frequency of matings between male genotype *i* and female genotype *j* is given by:

$$M_{ij} = g'_{jf} \frac{g'_{im} \frac{(\sigma_{ij}a_b + 1)(\xi_{ij}a_b + 1)}{z_b} \left((1 - c(1 - \varepsilon_i\gamma)) \left(\frac{\omega_i a_t + 1}{a_t + 2} \right) \right)}{z}$$

where

$$z = \sum_i g'_{im} \frac{(\sigma_{ij}a_b + 1)(\xi_{ij}a_b + 1)}{z_b} \left((1 - c(1 - \varepsilon_i\gamma)) \left(\frac{\omega_i a_t + 1}{a_t + 2} \right) \right)$$

$$z_b = ((1 - \rho_j)a_b + 1)b'_{1m} + (\rho_j a_b + 1)b'_{2m}$$

and where b'_{1m} and b'_{2m} are the frequencies of the two B alleles within males after viability selection, such that $b'_{1m} = g'_{1m} + g'_{2m} + g'_{5m} + g'_{6m}$ and $b'_{2m} = g'_{3m} + g'_{4m} + g'_{7m} + g'_{8m}$.

If the male allele at the B locus for genotype G_{*i*} is B₁ (*i*=1, 2, 5 or 6), $\varepsilon_i = 0$. If the male allele at the B locus for G_{*i*} is B₂ (*i*=3, 4, 7 or 8), $\varepsilon_i = 1$.

If the male allele at the T locus for G_{*i*} is T₂ (*i* is even), then $\omega_i = 1$, and $\omega_i = 0$ otherwise.

If the female allele at the R locus for G_{*j*} is R₂ (*j* > 4), $\rho_j = 1$, and $\rho_j = 0$ otherwise. In this version of the model, this shifts the mating bias from B₂ to B₁ males rather than simply turning the bias on and off.

Finally, if the male allele at the B locus for G_{*i*} is B₂ (*i*=3, 4, 7 or 8) **and** the female allele at the R locus for G_{*j*} is R₂ (*j* > 4), then $\sigma_{ij} = 1$, and $\sigma_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.

Similarly, we now have another term such if the male allele at the B locus for G_{*i*} is B₁ (*i*=1, 2, 5 or 6) **and** the female allele at the R locus for G_{*j*} is R₁ (*j* < 4), then $\xi_{ij} = 1$, and $\xi_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.

Note that again the z_b terms ultimately cancel out, but we have left them in place to preserve the interpretation of the numerator of the M_{ij} expression as the probability that a female of genotype G_j mates with a male of genotype G_i on her first territory visit.

For analysis and visualization, after recombination and mutation we again transformed the eight recursion equations into the equivalent seven equations for the allele frequencies at the three loci and first- and second-order linkage disequilibria (Bennett 1952).

To compare scenarios where the only difference in traits is the value of γ , we set s_r and s_b to zero. We started the population with r_2 and b_2 at 0.5 to control for frequency-dependent effects on the strength of sexual selection and started t_2 at the initial equilibrium frequency described in Appendix S2. We then calculated the magnitude of ΔR_2 in the second generation following the buildup of genetic correlations to assess for which values of γ (and other parameters) the female remodeling preference would be favored.

Reproducible code for this model and analysis can be found in the Mathematica notebook in Supporting Information File S3.

Literature Cited

Dhole S, Stern CA, Servedio MR. 2018 Direct detection of male quality can facilitate the evolution of female choosiness and indicators of good genes: Evolution across a continuum of indicator mechanisms. *Evolution* **72**(4), 770-784. (doi:10.1111/evo.13466).

Bennett JH. 1952 On the theory of random mating. *Annals of eugenics* **18**(4), 311-317. (doi: 10.1111/j.1469-1809.1952.tb02522.x).